

Revitalizing NHS England: Digital Transformation as a Catalyst for Public Reconnection

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Executive Summary:

The National Health Service (NHS) England is at a pivotal moment, facing unprecedented challenges but also significant opportunities for transformation. This paper explores how ongoing digital transformation efforts can serve as a catalyst for operational efficiency, improved patient care, and renewed public engagement.

Key Points:

1. The NHS is experiencing a crisis characterized by record-breaking waiting times, staff shortages, and declining public satisfaction.
2. Digital transformation presents an opportunity to address these challenges and revolutionize healthcare delivery.
3. Comprehensive training programs are crucial to bridge the digital skills gap among NHS staff and stakeholders.
4. Increased public engagement is an essential component of successful digital transformation in the NHS.
5. A multi-stakeholder approach to training can facilitate successful digital transformation and enhance public engagement.

The paper proposes a strategic approach to training and public engagement, emphasizing the need for continuous learning, cultural change, and leveraging new technologies. It concludes that by investing in its workforce and stakeholders through targeted, comprehensive training initiatives, NHS England can convert the current crisis into an opportunity for innovation and renewed public trust.

Introduction

The National Health Service (NHS England) stands at a critical juncture. However, amidst the challenges lies a unique opportunity for transformation and renewal. This paper explores how the ongoing digital transformation efforts within the NHS can serve not only to improve operational efficiency and patient care but also as a catalyst for reconnecting with the public and reshaping the future of healthcare delivery in the UK.

As we delve into the complexities of this transformation, we will examine the essential role of comprehensive training programs in bridging the digital skills gap among NHS staff and stakeholders. We will explore how these initiatives, when extended beyond the organization to include public education, can foster a new relationship between the NHS and the communities it serves.

By addressing the challenges head-on and embracing innovative approaches to training and engagement, NHS England has the potential to emerge from this crisis stronger, more efficient, and more closely aligned with the needs and expectations of 21st-century healthcare consumers.

The Research Question is: "How can a multi-stakeholder training approach address digital competency gaps among NHS staff, leadership, and the public to facilitate successful digital transformation and enhance public engagement in NHS England?"

Is the NHS Broken?

In 2023, Wickens and Brown of the Kings Fund reported a crisis in the NHS characterized by record-breaking waiting lists, exacerbated by high staff vacancy rates across various healthcare roles.² Some of their data was from 2022. This situation was further complicated by often outdated infrastructure, including aging buildings and equipment. According to Wickens and Brown (2023) these factors culminated in a system struggling to provide adequate access to care for many patients.

As a result, public satisfaction with the NHS plummeted to its lowest level on record, reflecting the widespread frustration and concern over the health service's ability to meet the population's needs.³ The state of the NHS appears to have been both a significant factor in the 2024 UK General Election and a priority for the new Labour Government, with Health Secretary Wes Streeting branding the NHS as "broken".⁴ However we will see later in this paper, that in the midst of crisis, the NHS may also be facing its greatest opportunity to reconnect with the public who are its real and greatest stakeholders.⁵

Low Public Satisfaction with the NHS – Statista⁶

However, the National Health Service (NHS) across the United Kingdom is already undergoing an extraordinary Digital Transformation to improve patient care, operational efficiency, and data-driven decision-making. This monumental effort is happening alongside long-awaited reforms to social care, which will mean many of the historical divisions between these two giants of British culture will begin to change and, in some cases, eventually disappear.^{7 8}

Public knowledge about, and engagement with this historic transition is still minimal, and people still hear more bad news than good news about the NHS.⁹ The current technology transitions, remain haunted by the ghosts of past failed projects like the NHS National Programme for IT (NPfIT), and the NHS has recently also faced waves of unprecedented cyberattacks.¹⁰

The NHS, one of the world's largest healthcare systems, is at a watershed moment. Unparalleled investments have already been made in clinical and data management infrastructure. 90% of Trusts in NHS England now have Electronic Patient Record Systems for example.¹¹ But the sheer size of the organisation means that the state of digital capabilities across the NHS workforce remains challenging. Digital skills are not just about how you work on computers and also affect the ways you work with people. Skills gaps (among both managers and staff) often only become clearer during or even after the introduction of the new technologies.

The NHS is not alone. The digital skills gap remains a widespread issue across the more developed nations, particularly in Europe.¹² This gap combines with staff shortages to pose a significant challenge to the NHS's Digital Transformation efforts.^{13 14}

There are several possible alternative NHS models:

- Social health insurance (e.g., France, Germany)
- Greater use of private self-pay and insurance
- Expanded charging for NHS services
- Hypothecated taxes for healthcare
- Merging NHS and Social Care (Current NHS England proposal)

However, this paper does not focus on the current changes to the structure of NHS England and Social Care.¹⁵ Rather, this paper aims to show that the success of this unprecedented NHS Digital Transformation hinges *on the approach to training*. This is the ONE crucial factor above all; often overlooked, underrated or undelivered. We will also show how the training within the NHS must then also be extended beyond the organisation to help create a new relationship with the public.

So far, we have discussed the current crisis in the UK's National Health Service (NHS), outlined the ongoing digital transformation efforts and challenges, emphasized the fundamental importance of training in the NHS, and in its relationship with the public. *Next, we will look at how technology change impacts people in the workplace.*

Technology and People

The development of the digital economy means that we must help improve digital competencies of staff and patients.¹⁶ In the NHS there is already a clear realisation that Digital Transformation is not merely a technology upgrade;^{17,18} Since the technology transition also presents a fundamental shift in how health and social care will be delivered and managed, this will in turn mean a real change in the relationship between the NHS and the public. To accomplish the full potential of this transformation, a comprehensive and strategic new approach to staff training is essential. The places and nature of the training delivery will also need to change even more than currently. Part of that training will also need to be “public education”. More on that shortly.

Ibrahim Ali Al-Baher (2024) shows how Digital Transformation is already reshaping the nature of employee training and development, emphasizing the need for continuous learning, cultural change, and leveraging new technologies to enhance skills and attract talent.¹⁹ For David Mainville (2024) the personal impact of workplace changes on staff, is one of the crucial factors in Digital Transformation and requires a revamped change management strategy, focussed on *people* as much as on *technology*.²⁰

Al-Baher (2024) posits that successful Digital Transformation inherently requires organizations to reconsider their training programs and develop more effective strategies for human resource development. This perspective aligns with research by Barykin et al. (2020), who proposed an expanding the definitions of digital competence, distinguishing between digital competence and digital literacy, and emphasizing the importance of practical, hands-on experience in developing the new digital competencies, even including the use of digital twins.²¹

A report by the Chartered Institute of Personnel Development (CIPD) in 2020 showed that workers across organisations still felt that their skills development has a lower priority during Digital Transformations.²² The same CIPD report showed that employees who are consulted about technology changes are more likely to view the impacts positively and to believe the change will lead to improvements in job quality.

Hendy et al. (2005) draw important lessons from history noting that previous NHS leadership did not adequately address the human challenges (including training deficiencies), within some past unsuccessful Digital Transformation efforts.²³ Hendy et al. (2005) also report that NHS staff responsible for implementation of previous technology transitions described low morale, due to factors like poor communication from leadership and unrealistic timelines.

The best corporate learning plans build interrelated digital competencies across all levels of the organisation, fostering a dynamic culture of cross-functional collaboration, motivation and innovation through blended learning, ensuring smooth transition and adoption of the targeted Digital Transformation outcomes.²⁴ Takian (2012) highlights the example of a hospital that "conducted 700 workflow familiarization sessions" instead of

generic classroom training, focusing on integrating the Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems into existing work processes.²⁵

We have now emphasized the importance of developing digital competencies among NHS staff and patients as a fundamental shift in healthcare delivery relationships. We have also shown this will need a new strategic approach to staff training, including public education. Next, we will look at possible future directions for training for NHS England.

New Training for NHS England

The ongoing digital transformation of healthcare services presents both challenges and opportunities for NHS staff at all levels, as well as the relationship of the NHS with the public. Comprehensive and accessible training programmes are urgently required to help equip not just NHS staff but also other stakeholders at all levels with the knowledge, skills, and mindset needed.

The NHS offers some guidance and resources for digital skills.²⁶ This has the benefits of addressing local needs but means that implementation can differ considerably across the NHS Trusts. These new training programmes must integrate with and build upon the work being done within the NHS and help make this type of training available more consistently.²⁷

Digivertex Ltd has designed a comprehensive training program, specifically for NHS personnel and stakeholders. The training and consultancy we provide covers a range of topics crucial for the modern healthcare environment, from basic digital literacy to advanced concepts in healthcare technology, implementation and management. The courses and facilitated sessions align with the Digital Skills Framework, the goals of the Digital Academy, and other existing NHS initiatives.

Key Focus Areas:

1. Understanding Digital Transformation in Healthcare
2. Systems Thinking and Facilitating Change
3. Essential Digital Skills for Healthcare Professionals
4. Innovation and Continuous Learning in Digital Healthcare
5. Improving Patient Care through Digital Technologies
6. Ethical Considerations and Data Security in Digital Health
7. Community Engagement in Digital Healthcare

The Digivertex training aims to foster a culture of innovation, enhance teamwork, and develop leadership capabilities in managing digital change. It covers important aspects such as cybersecurity, Electronic Patient Records (EPR) systems, telemedicine, the integration of social care with NHS digital processes, and much more.

For more Senior Leaders, the Digivertex program offers additional modules focused on strategies for driving digital change, fostering a digital-first mindset, and leading digital project management initiatives in healthcare settings.

Digivertex is already in consultations that are contributing to a new framework of skills requirements for trainers and instructional designers for the NHS. Utilising existing and new resources, the new framework learns from the current guidelines for clinical practitioners. It also facilitates a new structured approach to engaging with clinical leads as subject specialists (SMEs) in training design and delivery. Several important direct benefits and other outcomes of this approach have been identified. If you wish to engage with us on that process, please contact us (admin [at] digivertex.ltd).

Public engagement in health has gained significant footing in recent years, even becoming enshrined in some legislation and policy. However, debate persists about effective engagement methods and impact measurement. While traditionally criticized for lacking robust evidence, a stronger evidence base is emerging as public engagement processes become more sophisticated. There's an increasing focus on documenting impact and developing more comprehensive approaches to engagement throughout research and service design processes.^{28 29}

Digivertex has nearly two decades of training and facilitating engagement by organisational leaders with their stakeholder communities and utilising digital media. Though there are risks, public engagement can lead to numerous benefits, including better health outcomes, identification of unique health needs, and enhanced research design. It can improve implementation and dissemination of findings, provide psychological and social benefits for participants, and facilitate new learning for both the public and the organisation. When done inclusively, it has the potential to reduce health inequalities and increase accountability and transparency in health services.

The current crisis in NHS England is therefore also a major opportunity to re-engage with staff and the public. By investing in its workforce and other stakeholders through targeted and comprehensive training initiatives, NHS England can convert the moment of crisis into an opportunity for a new kind of public engagement, positioning itself again at the forefront of digital healthcare innovation and culture, setting a new standard for healthcare systems worldwide.

We have outlined the need for comprehensive training programs to support the digital transformation of NHS England, introducing Digivertex's work in this area and emphasizing the importance of public engagement. Next, we will look at potential problems in these processes.

Addressing Potential Challenges

There will likely be cost and resource allocation challenges in the approach proposed in this paper, but the potential benefits (if well executed) outweigh the costs and other risks. There could also be some resistance to change among staff which can be managed through engagement, understanding and addressing their concerns. Keeping pace with

rapid technological advancements during a planned change project is now more a challenge than ever before. But active tracking of costs and potential benefits will help decisions on specification changes if these are needed.

The emergence of new technologies in any society can also cause social and economic disruptions. A well-quoted example of this is the invention of affordable mobile phones.³⁰ Similarly, the process of Digital Transformation in any organisation can introduce levels of internal disruption, some of them unexpected.

Pritesh Mistry's blog article from the Kings Fund (2023), says that the impact of the ongoing Digital Transformation in the NHS also necessitates a change in leadership approaches. According to Mistry, the implementation of digital technologies in the NHS is already causing a fragmentation of the traditional compartmentalization of resources, risks, and benefits across different parts of the system.³¹ While the breaking down of historic operational silos is probably beneficial, Mistry highlights two interesting examples of possible unintended consequences, during NHS Digital Transformations

- New data and clinical management software like Electronic Patient Records systems (EPR) also bring risks that computer time for clinicians will significantly increase over time spent with patients.
- Virtual Wards, while increasing home-based care for patients and expanding hospital capacity may also raise community healthcare staff workloads.^{32 33}

Mistry, et al., (2022), write contrary to traditional views, that technology alone is insufficient for interoperability. Building and strengthening human relationships across organizational areas and professions will be crucial, requiring dedicated time and space away from daily responsibilities.³⁴ Mistry, (2023), says this means that successful leaders in the new digital NHS will need to collaborate more and break down operational silos.³⁵

According to Mistry et al., (2022), leadership plays a vital role in minimizing power dynamics and supporting staff to lead Digital Transformation projects. The Mistry report also emphasizes the importance of communication in reinforcing a collaborative working culture.³⁶

NHS leaders at various levels will need training to help them evolve both the ideas and practice in the leadership styles. The NHS has started to emphasize the use of Systems Thinking, an approach that examines how various systems and components, even seemingly unrelated ones, function, interact, and influence each other. In practice, we often rely on mental models - our beliefs, assumptions, and values - to understand and interact with these factors in our lives and work. The new training should help NHS staff and stakeholders better utilise these models to shape our actions and decisions regarding complex systems.³⁷ Please contact us (admin [at] digivertex.ltd) for more information on our training and consultancy packages.

We have discussed some potential challenges in implementing the proposals in this paper, highlighting the importance of evolving appropriate collaborative leadership

styles, utilizing systems thinking and contextual mental models. Next, we will draw some conclusions.

Conclusion and Future Directions

The Digital Transformation of the NHS represents a pivotal moment in the evolution of healthcare delivery in the UK. While the challenges are significant, including concerned public opinion, political headwinds, resource allocation issues, staff resistance to change, and the need to keep pace with rapid technological advancements; the potential benefits far outweigh the risks.

The importance of trainers and training in digital transformation has been underestimated, despite their crucial role in realizing the benefits of technological changes.³⁸ Occupational trainers play a pivotal role in successful digital transformation, particularly in complex integrations like that of the NHS and Social Care. The work of Trainers can also form the basis of a wider integration of NHS stakeholders and the public into the Digital Transformation process.

By investing in comprehensive training programs, fostering a culture of innovation, and prioritizing public engagement, the NHS can transform this moment of crisis into an opportunity for renewal and reconnection with its stakeholders.

Looking ahead, several key areas warrant further exploration and development:

1. Continuous evaluation and adaptation of these training programs to ensure they remain aligned with evolving technological trends and healthcare needs.
2. Development of even more sophisticated metrics to measure the impact of digital transformation on patient outcomes, staff job satisfaction, and public perception of the NHS.
3. Exploration of innovative public engagement strategies that further leverage digital platforms to enhance communication and collaboration between the NHS and the communities it serves.
4. Further research into the long-term effects of digital transformation on healthcare delivery models, workforce dynamics, and patient experiences.
5. Investigation of potential partnerships with academic institutions and technology companies to drive innovation and research in aspects of digital healthcare.

As the NHS navigates this transformative period, it can set a new global standard for healthcare systems worldwide. By embracing digital innovation, prioritizing comprehensive training, and fostering meaningful public engagement,³⁹ the NHS can not only overcome its current challenges but also emerge as a more resilient, efficient, and responsive healthcare system for generations to come. The journey ahead is complex, but with a commitment to continuous learning, adaptation, collaboration, and public engagement, the NHS can reaffirm its position as a cornerstone of British society and a beacon of excellence in global healthcare.

A multi-stakeholder training approach could therefore help address digital competency gaps among NHS staff, leadership, and the public to facilitate successful digital transformation and enhance public engagement in NHS England.

¹ Additional research for this paper was done using claude.ai

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